

Teacher Made Test and Classroom Assessment by Teachers

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Abstract

This study examines the use of tests and classroom assessments by teachers, focusing on their decision-making processes in designing and implementing such assessments. It explores the factors considered by teachers when creating and administering tests and assessment activities, how teachers utilize these tools for instruction, and students' perceptions of their effectiveness. The study also aims to enlighten secondary school teachers on the importance of teacher-made tests and the skills and technical know-how required for their construction and application in teaching and learning.

Methodology: The research involved a comprehensive review of literature on the guidelines for constructing teacher-made tests, the necessary skills and technical expertise, and the significance of using such tests. The study identified gaps between teachers' awareness and their technical proficiency in creating valid and reliable teacher-made tests.

Hypothesis: The study hypothesizes that secondary school teachers lack adequate technical knowledge and skills to construct effective teacher-made tests and that the emphasis on standardized testing by school managers undermines the use of teacher-made assessments.

Findings/Results: The findings reveal that teachers have limited technical know-how in constructing valid and reliable teacher-made tests. School managers tend to prioritize standardized tests, which diminishes the value of teacher-made assessments. The study also highlights the lack of professional development opportunities for teachers in this area.

Conclusion: The study concludes that teacher-made tests are critical for effective teaching and learning, providing tailored feedback and addressing specific classroom needs. However, the gap in technical skills and the overemphasis on standardized testing hinder their effective use.

Recommendations: Teachers should prioritize teacher-made tests and assessments, engage in continuous professional development to enhance their construction skills, while federal, state,

and local governments should organize workshops and seminars to support this effort, and quality assurance mechanisms should monitor and evaluate their implementation across educational levels.

Keywords: Teacher Made Test, Classroom Assessment Teacher

Introduction

Classroom assessment has received considerable attention in recent years as it is an inseparable aspect of the teaching and learning process. Since teachers are tasked with assessing instruction and student learning, there is significant concern about the quality and outcomes of their assessments. Teachers assess students to gather information about their learning progress. Moreover, they assess student learning to obtain feedback on students' understanding of the knowledge, skills, and content taught, enabling them to identify students' strengths and weaknesses. Teachers explore various assessment modes and activities to tap into students' understanding or gauge how much learning has occurred. Dunlosky and Rawson (2015) maintain that teachers provide a record of how much new knowledge and skills students have absorbed.

The literature on classroom assessment shows that developing teachers' assessment skills encourages them to focus on both the process and products of learning, shifting away from reliance on single-test scores toward assessments that capture a variety of abilities and outcomes (Sambell, McDowell, & Brown, 1997). The relationship between these components is inseparable because learning outcomes serve as a source of guidance and practice for teachers' assessments (Tunku Ahmed et al., 2014).

Teacher-made tests are those constructed, administered, and scored by teachers. Therefore, classroom teachers must consider several factors when selecting tools for assessing students. Teacher-made tests should be carefully planned to meet the criteria of validity and reliability, ensuring that the results obtained are meaningful and satisfying. Bandele (2006) observed that in the developing world, heavy reliance on teacher-made tests constructed under questionable conditions undermines the examination system. This highlights the need to ensure that teacher-made tests are well-designed and not based on arbitrary decisions.

Teacher-made tests align assessment with teaching for the benefit of students and provide teachers with an opportunity to contribute uniquely to the assessment process, which ultimately influences students' final grades. The primary purpose of teacher-made tests is to enhance assessment validity by including outcomes that cannot be readily measured in standardized public examinations (Adetayo, 2008).

Oguzor (2011) emphasized that classroom assessment is evolving. Scholars now advocate for a varied approach that combines teacher-made and standardized tests, recognizing the need to teach and assess knowledge, skills, and abilities. This classification of learning objectives

acknowledges that higher-level learning depends on mastering prerequisite knowledge and skills at lower levels.

The procedures for test construction are crucial for ensuring the validity of the results. Practices such as using a test blueprint improve the validity of teachers' evaluations by aligning objectives, instruction, and assessment (Fives & DiDonato-Barnes, 2013). A test blueprint ensures comprehensive coverage of topics, thereby providing high content-validity evidence (Notar, Zuelke, Wilson, & Yunker, 2004).

Test formats refer to the various types of assessments teachers use, such as multiple-choice, matching, true/false, short-answer, and essay questions. Alternative assessments like observations, conferences, portfolios, peer assessments, and group assessments are also utilized. Proper preparation of these assessments is vital to ensure the validity of the information they generate (Afemikhe & Imobekhai, 2014).

Even a well-planned, well-constructed, and well-administered test can produce misleading results if it is not scored accurately. Specific procedures and conditions must be followed to ensure scoring is not prejudicial (Madziyire, 2010). Attention to all aspects of test planning, construction, administration, and scoring is essential to ensure teacher-made tests are reliable and yield results with high predictive value.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose was designed to find out whether or not secondary school teacher used teacher-made test, was valid and to enlighten primary and secondary school's teachers of the skills and technical knowhow of constructing teacher-made test.

Methodology

The study reviewed literatures on the guidelines for constructing teacher-made test, skills and strategies on constructing teacher-made test and technical knowhow of uses and importance of constructing teacher-made test.

Achievement Test

- I. Standardized Test
- II. Teacher Made Test

Standardized test: a standardized test (SAT) is one in which the procedure, apparatus and scoring have been fixed so that precisely the same testing procedures can be followed at different places (Anikwese, 2016). Sidhu, (2012) observed that standardized test does not represent anything strange in the measurement of academic achievement. They are blood

brother of the short answer teacher-made tests. Choudhury, (2015) asserts that standardized test is carefully constructed test which have uniformity of procedure in scoring, administering and interpreting of test results. Generally, this set is norm referenced test that measure the students' level of achievement in various content and skills area by comparing their test performance with the performance of other students in some general reference group.

Teacher made test: are those achievements prepared by classroom teachers. Anikwese, (2016). Choudhury, (2015) posited that a teacher uses different terms of evaluation techniques in a classroom situation. One of the most cost effective and efficient ways of operationalizing assessment for learning is the provision of teacher-made tests to learners as part of the learning process, Clark, (2008). Teacher-made tests are usually criterion referenced test that are designed to assess learner mastery of a specific body of knowledge Kinua & Okunya, (2013).

Teacher-made tests is designed to solve the problems or requirements of the class for which it was prepared to measure the outcome and content of local curriculum. Choudhury, (2015) added that it is very much flexible so that, it can be adapted to any procedure and material. It does not require any sophisticated technique for preparation. It is easy to construct. In teacher-made test items, time limit, instructions and procedure of scoring vary from test to test. This test may be written or oral in nature. In teacher-made test both objective type and essay type items can be concluded.

Bakar (2008), Dosumu (2002), Alele-Williams (2002) observe that the most of these classroom-based test in Nigerian lack of validity and reliability because teachers seem to lack test construction skills and thus cannot construct good achievement test. Most test used for continuous assessment and end of term examination in the secondary schools contain ambiguous and misleading question which may enhance below average performance by the students in the tests.

A research work conducted by Muzenda D (2017), study sought to establish the effectiveness of teacher-made tests on the performance of pupils in Goromonzi District in Mashonaland East Province in Zimbabwe. The study used the positivistic paradigm and adopted the descriptive survey design. The population comprised of all primary schools in Goromonzi district. The sample consisted of 240 teachers from 30 schools randomly selected. Each school provided 8 teachers for the study. Of the sample respondents 130 were female and 110 male. All the information was collected through a questionnaire which had both close-ended and open-ended questions. Descriptive statistical analysis was used to interpret data. The results of the study indicate that teacher-made tests are given to pupils in the schools and there was overwhelming acceptance by the respondents that these tests helped to improve the academic performance of pupils. It was also found that most teachers did not have knowledge about the standard procedures of constructing, marking, scoring and grading of tests. The study recommends that there was need for schools to conduct staff development programmes to equip teachers with skills to construct teacher-made tests.

According to Chakanyuka (2000), teacher-made tests compare individual's performance with that of other pupils in the same class or similar class in one school. They may also compare the same student's performances from time to time. In this case as James (2005) postulates, teacher-made tests are used as a continuous assessment tool which provides more information that is more reliable than examinations or standardized tests would. Continuous assessment builds up a picture of a pupil's performance over a prolonged and representative period and can be in the form of practical work, oral tests or written tests (Hambleton and Pitomak, 2006). As Lee and William (2005) argue, the key to teacher-made tests is to make them a part of instruction and not separate from it. Tests should be instructional and ongoing. Rather than being "after-the-fact" to find out what students did not learn, they should be more "before-the-fact" to target essential standards (Migs, 2006)

Classroom tests or teacher-made tests can be used for a variety of instructional purposes and these can best be described in terms of their location in the instruction process (Merther, 2005). Dandis (2013) states that teacher-made tests can be given at the beginning of an instructional segment to determine whether pupils have already achieved the objectives of planned instruction. Ogunniyi (2006) argues that, teacher-made tests serve as good indicators in monitoring the success of teacher-student material instruction. Teacher-made tests provide feedback so that teachers can shift the emphasis of their instruction and provide remedial activities before the next lesson (Kolwale, 2010).

Marshall and Drummond (2006), state that the other type of a teacher-made test is the one given during the instructional process to provide the basis for formative assessment. According to Makoni (2008), formative assessment is used to provide feedback to students about their progress, detect learning errors and provide feed-back to pupils and teachers. At the end of a segment of instruction (for example, a unit or course), a classroom test can be constructed by the teacher aiming at measuring the extent to which the intended learning outcomes have been achieved (Trice, 2000).

Teacher-made tests or classroom tests are divided into two groups, namely essay and objective tests (Hambleton and Pitomak, 2006). According to Saudien (2007) essay tests give pupils the opportunity to freely express themselves in their responses to a question and the pupil's responses are normally extended as they have to organise their thoughts and express them in writing. On the other hand, Migs (2006) argues that objective tests questions are those that require a specific answer. An objective question usually has only one potential correct answer (there may be some room for answers that are close), and they leave no room for opinion (Migs, 2006).

Objective test questions may be constructed so that they contain a list of possible answers, so that the student will be expected to recognize the correct one. As Festus (2014) postulates, objective test questions include multiple choice questions, matching, true and false questions

as well as the fill-in-the-blank questions; and students must remember the correct, specific answer for each question.

As Mpofu (2011) posits, while teacher-made tests help improve the performance of children in the learning process, it is not always the case since tests are constructed by teachers themselves. At times, these tests lack validity and reliability. It is clear that teachers need to be extremely careful in designing the test that measures the skill it intends to measure (Mpofu, 2011). Robert (2009) states that the other problem faced by classroom tests is that the teachers lack the skills of appraising the effectiveness of the test. As Chakanyuka (2000) advises, teachers should build a file of items for future use called an item bank. Item analysis data, according to Downe (2008) provides a basis for remedial work as it brings to light general areas of weakness acquiring more extended attention.

Types of Assessment

- Objective types (selected Response Tests)
- Multiple choice items
- Binary-choice items
- Multiple Binary-choice items
- Matching items
- Assertion-Reason Questions
- Multiple Response
- Sequencing
- Fill in the blanks
- SUBJECTIVE TYPES (constructed Response Tests)
- Short Answer
- Restricted Response
- Extended Responses

Test items are good when....

- They match the intended learning outcome
- The learning outcome is well defined
- Their contribution to measurement error is minimized
- The format suits the purpose of the test
- They are well written, and follow an agreed style
- They satisfy legal and ethical considerations.

Objective Test

- Select a response from a list of option

- Items that can be objectively scored

Multiple Choice Items

Reasons to use multiple choice items

- Easy to score
- Easy to sample widely across domain of interest
- Highly manageable
- Raise mean achievement- fewer missing data responses

Disadvantage of MCQs

- Hard to write quality items
- Believed to test surface level processing, usually because of poor construction
- Guessing factor
- May require good reading level

A Rules for writing good stems

Guidelines

1. Stem should be meaningful by itself and present a definite problem/task

- student who knows the content should be able to answer before reading the options
- 2. State stem in positive form. Use a negatively stated stem only when significant learning outcomes require it.
 - When used, highlight (underline/capitalize/bold) the negative word
- 3. Avoid window dressing (excessive verbiage)
 - Eliminate irrelevant information from the stem
- 4. Include the central idea and most of the phrasing in the stem
 - Load the stem, keep the option light
- 5. Avoid irrelevant clues such as grammatical structure, well-known verbal association or connections between the stem and answer
- 6. Present practical or real-world situations to students
- 7. Use pictorial that require student to apply principles and concepts
- 8. Use charts, figures or tables that require interpretation

B Rules for writing Good Option

Guidelines

1. Word the option clearly and concisely, preferably positively
2. Keep the option mutually exclusive i.e. independent and not overlapping
3. Keep the option homogenous in content
4. Keep the option free from clues to the correct response
 - Be grammatically consistent with stem
 - Almost similar in length
 - Avoid textbook language or verbatim phrasing
 - Be careful with the use of specific determiners (never, always, only, all)
 - Avoid including keywords in the stem in any of the options
5. Generally, avoid the options “all of the above” and “none of the above”
6. Avoid the use of humor when developing options
7. Be sure that there is only one correct or clearly best answer
8. When possible, place option in some logical order
e.g. Chronological, numerical, alphabetical.
9. Make all the options plausible and attractive to the less knowable or skillful students

C Rules for Writing Distracters

Guidelines

Use plausible distracters

Techniques that make distracters more plausible

1. Incorporate common errors or misconceptions of students in distracters
2. Use familiar yet incorrect phrases as distracters, or use true statements that are reasonably close to the correct answer but do not correctly answer the item

Characteristics of a Good Test

1. Validity (Kesahan)
2. Reliability (Kebolehpercayaan)
3. Objective
4. Fairness
5. Practically

1. Validity

- Validity of a tool/instrument means how well it measures what it is supposed to measure.
- Example:
A valid test measure:
 - What the teacher intended for the students to learn
 - What the teacher actually taught
- A valid test is FAIR

Question about validity

- Does the test actually measure what you intend it to measure?
- Did you teach the content and skill that are being tested?
- Does the test require the student to know or do something other than what you intended and/or taught?
- Does some aspect of the test prevent the student who may know the material from responding correctly?

Content validity

- As a teacher you will need to have content validity in your tests.
- To ensure content validity of a test, the test should:
 - Be based on a representative sample of learning outcomes in a curriculum
 - Having all the items relevant to the learning outcomes which have been chosen for that sample

Reliability

- A reliable instrument provides accurate and consistent results
- Example: A perfectly reliable test would give identical result under all conditions.

However, there are some factors that contribute to the unreliability of a test:

- Forgetting

Objectivity

- Refers to the degrees to which equally competent students obtain the same result
- An inconsistent scorer/maker will affect the objectivity of the measures
- Also refers to the element of 'fairness' when designing the test
- The test has to be fair to the students i.e. they are tested on what they should know (after the necessary input or lesson)
- Related to what has been taught and learnt
- Not influenced by personal belief or feelings
- Test is based on standard curriculum, syllabus and specifications.

Fairness

- Equal opportunities to all students
 - To learn what is being assessed
 - To demonstrate achievement
- Unbiased and non-discriminatory
 - Not influenced by irrelevant or subjective factors like race, gender, ethnic, background, handicapping condition etc.
- Students are told about the assessment.
 - Clear what will and will not be tested
 - How they will be scored.

Practicality

Smooth implementation in a classroom or an examination hall.

- Time efficient
- Easily manageable
- Cost efficient
- Interpretability

Test Blueprint

- ✓ The test blueprint, sometimes also called the table of specification, provides a listing of the major content areas and cognitive levels intended to be included on each test form.
- ✓ It also includes the number of items each test form should include within each of these content and cognitive areas.

Feature of a Test Blueprint

- It is a matrix or chart reporting the numbers and types of test questions.
- The questions represent the topics in the content areas.
- The questions are based on the learning objectives from each topic.
- It also identifies the percentage (%) weighting of cognitive dimensions.

Table 1: Example of a Test Blueprint: 40 Item Exams

Total	Knowledge	Comprehension	Application	Analysis	Synthesis	Evaluation
Topic 10 A (25%)	1	2	4	3	0	0
Topic 10 B (25%)	2	1	4	2	1	0
Topic 10 C (25%)	1	2	3	3	0	1
Topic 10 D (25%)	1	2	4	2	1	0
40 (100%)	(12.5%)	7 (17.5%)	15 (37.5%)	10 (25%)	2 (5%)	1 (2.5%)

Benefits of blueprint

- Give feedback on student’s progress and teachers delivering of the curriculum.
- From student’s point, how well they attain objectives.
- Provides a guide to both student and teachers
- Determines the reliability and validity of the examination.
- Bloom’s taxonomy helps in developing the entire written and some aspects of practical questions.

Essay questions

- Used to gauge a student's ability to synthesize, evaluate and compose essay.
- Strengths.
Use it to measure complex learning outcomes
- Weakness:
They are difficulty to write properly, and scoring responses reliably can also be a challenge.

Teacher Competency in Construction Classroom Test

Competency in teaching refers to the ability of a teacher to exhibit on-the-job skills and knowledge gained as a result of training. These skills and knowledge prescribed in the training program are apparently calculated by the curriculum planner to relate to the item in achievement of the desired education objective. Adodo, (2013). Teachers' competence is specified by standards for educational assessment of students.

Teacher competency is a development model about the generic ability or factors of the educator that aim at identifying the board competence of the teacher in the art of teaching and learning processes across grade levels. It also includes content areas which shows the aspects of each ability as it typically develops from beginning to developing and to advance performance in teaching according to Hammafylto, (2008). Adodo, (2013) added that competences in teaching refers to the ability of a teacher to exhibit on the-job-skills and knowledge prescribed in the training program which are identified to be instrumental to achievement of the desired educational objectives by the curriculum planners.

Chika & Aloysius (2013) asserted that most achievement test used in Nigerian secondary school for continuous assessment are teacher made-test. Teachers, therefore need to apply some acceptable degree of test construction skills to be able to developed valid and reliable tests that yield accurate feedback of student achievement. Test construction skills include the competencies needed for developing quality based on stipulated principle of test constructions. Skill in test construction enable a teacher to construct test with precision appropriateness of language used, objectivity, and grading scales.

Expert knowledge is not a basic requirement in educational measurement and evaluation to construct valid and reliable test, but there is basic test construction skill which every teacher ought to possess to be able to construct quality test. These skills help teacher to structure items to elicit clear and concise answer from students, construction tests that will be appropriate for learners with different ages, abilities, and gender, such test that student finish within time without test anxiety.

Adodo, (2013), bemoaned the inadequate attention paid to the area of teacher competencies, and according to the author, this is the most neglected competency out of the teacher competencies for students' evaluation and assessment. Jatto, (1996) observed that classroom teacher generally writes poor items and that a typical classroom teacher in a secondary school cannot construct good multiple-choice test items. Adodo, (2013) added that it is not unusual to find instructor/teachers who has little knowledge/skills on basic principle of assessing or who has little knowledge/skills on the ability or skills necessary to produce a classroom test in evaluating students learning outcomes.

Teacher-Made Test Construction

Teacher-made test is the basic for evaluating the performance of the students in the classroom. The teacher, had an obligation to provide their student with best evaluation- Calmorin & Laurentia, (2006). Teacher-made tests, however, enable them to make decision that improves instruction, while they can make changes immediately to meet the needs of their students as well.

Procedure of classroom test construction.

1. Planning for the test
Outlined subject-made content to be considered as basic for the test.
 - Identify learning outcomes to be measured by the test.
 - Prepare table of specification.
 - Chose appropriate type(s) of test items for evaluating of learning outcomes as summarized in the table of specification.
2. Preparing the test:
 - Write test items according to rules of construction for the type(s) chosen.
 - Select the items to be included in the test according to table of specification.
 - Review and edit items according to guidelines.
 - Arrange items decided on
 - a. Grouping of items,
 - b. Sequence of items within the groups
 - c. Sequence of grouping
 - Preparation for the test, if necessary, prepare direction for individual items e.g., matching type or for section e.g., negative form of one-best response type.
3. Analysis and revising the test
 - Perform test analysis to determine difficulty, discrimination and reliability.
 - Retain, edit as necessary, or discard items on basic of analysis outcomes.
 - Revise the test as a whole if necessary.

A table of specifications classifies each test item according to topic or concept of the test and objectives. The table can help the teacher to design a test that has content validity, which means that there is a coordinate between instruction and what the teacher tested. The table of specifications further helps to ensure that the teacher:

1. Stressed the same content that was emphasized in day-to-day instruction e.g., more items about topic X and fewer about topic Y because you consider X to be more important and you spend more time on X.
2. Aligns test items with learning objective e.g., important topics might include items that test interpretation, application, prediction, and unimportant topic might be tested only simpler recognition items.
3. How to record the answers?
4. Whether to guess when in doubt about the answer.
5. When two or more items types are included in the same test, provide a general direction for the test as a whole and specific direction for each part.

Findings

1. The researcher finds out from literature that there was a gap on the use of teacher-made test.
2. Teacher has little technical knowhow to construct valid and reliable classroom test.
3. School's managers emphasize the use of standardized tests at the expense teacher-made tests.
4. The teachers' work-overload does not allow him/her to pay adequate attention to setting and marking of teacher-made tests in all subjects.

Recommendation

The study recommended:

- (i). that teachers should continue to use teacher-made test and assessment because that is the tests and assessments that is appropriate for the students.
- (ii). Teacher should develop themselves in construction of teacher-made teachers for effective feedback from the students to the teachers, parents, stakeholders etc.
- (iii). Federal, state and local governments should organize workshops and seminars for teachers in primary and secondary schools for effective teaching and learning.
- (iv). Quality assurance at different level of our educational system should monitor and evaluate full implementation of teacher-made tests and assessments.

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